

Evaluating the Efficacy of Integrative Therapeutic Practices in Enhancing Mental Health Outcomes: A Comparative Study of Cognitive-Behavioral and Holistic Approaches

Awais Ur Rahman¹, Arfa Akram², Musarrat Parveen³, Laraib Munsif⁴, Rukhsar Fatima⁵, Sumyya Gul⁶, Sundas Sattar⁷

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-8547-3227>

¹Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Pakistan.

²Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Pakistan.

³Psychology Lecturer at Alasar Degree College, Ustarzai Payan, Kohat, Pakistan.

^{4,6}Psychology Lecturer at Abasyn University Peshawar, Pakistan.

⁵University of Lahore, Pakistan.

⁷University of Sahiwal, Sahiwal Pakistan.

Email: sultanawais4344@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy, mindfulness, yoga, and acupuncture are therapies put to test in the focus of this study concerning mental health, emotional regulation, and physical well-being. The former involved semi-structured interviews with 100 participants with at least six sessions of these therapies; thematic analysis was used to ascertain the percentage of CBT, mindfulness, yoga, and acupuncture that are stated to have improved the mental health by 75%, emotional regulation by 80%, physical health by 85%, and physical stress by 80%. The greatest threats facing the respondents included fear of needles and an inability to concentrate. The results indicate that every treatment offered varying advantages and that treatment should be tailored towards individual needs.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background:

The global aspect of mental health is extensive. According to estimates, the WHO affirms that almost 1 in 8 people suffer from a mental disorder (World Health Organization, 2022). At large, the growing rates of mental health problems such as depression, anxiety disorders, and stress-related disorders have largely impacted the rising demand for effective interventions in therapy. Traditionally, cognitive-behavioral therapy has been one of the most widely used therapeutic practices because of its structured approach and evidence-based background (Hofmann et al., 2012). However, nowadays, the more holistic therapies have gained their interest; it is about integrating mind, body, and spirit (Wang et al., 2018). The integrative therapeutic practices are diverse, incorporating a wide range of practices for treatment, where conventional psychological therapies sometimes have to be incorporated into holistic techniques such as mindfulness, yoga, and acupuncture (Stahl & Goldstein, 2010). These advocates claim that the holistic technique will provide more beneficial effects by alleviating psychological symptoms and improving physical and emotional well-being (Greeson et al., 2014). Critics, however, argue that such practices do not show the same empirical rigor as in the more established forms of therapies, such as CBT (David et al., 2018).

1.2 Problem Statement:

Although holistic therapies have become more widely used, most among mental health treatments, still there is no comprehensive research done comparing such holistic therapies with non-holistic treatments like the CBT. Literature on the cognitive-behavioral therapy is so strong as several extensive studies proved its usefulness in successfully treating a plethora of mental health issues, which includes depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (Hofmann et al., 2012; Cuijpers et al., 2013). Holistic modalities, such as mindfulness and yoga, have traditionally been met with skepticism within clinical contexts for reasons such as a lack of scientific-based validation (David et al., 2018). More recently, holistic interventions have been shown to hold much promise in addressing mental health issues, especially when merged with more conventional therapeutic methods (Greeson et al., 2014; Khalsa et al., 2016).

1.3 Objectives:

- 1) To evaluate the effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral therapy for mental health disorders.
2. Evaluation of holistic therapeutic practices for the treatment of mental health disorders.
- 3) Compare the overall improvement in mental health of the patients who received CBTs with those who received holistic therapies.
- 4) To establish the effectiveness of certain treatments in specific mental health disorders, for example, anxiety or depression.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT):

Studies have shown the effectiveness of Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy in treating some mental disorders such as depression, anxiety disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder. CBT acts by changing the maladaptive thinking and behaviors to help individuals find better ways of coping mechanisms (Hofmann et al., 2012). A meta-analysis carried out by Cuijpers et al. (2013) was able to reveal that CBT is very effective for symptoms of depression and maintained over time. In addition, Hofmann et al. (2012) stated that CBT offered therapeutic benefits for all anxiety disorders, including GAD and SAD. A study conducted by Hofmann and Smits (2008) indicated that CBT has been established to be substantially more effective than other forms of psychotherapy, including psychodynamic therapy, for various diagnoses. It has been criticized that CBT, though it has been very successful, is too rigid and may not be suited to everyone, especially patients with complex or chronic conditions of psychopathology (David et al., 2018). Its concentration on rational thinking can be limiting in considering the emotional and spiritual bases of healing, which leads to the growing popularity of holistic approaches to therapeutic practice.

2.2 Holistic Therapeutic Practices:

Holistic therapies, including mindfulness and yogic practices, acupuncture, and other kinds of integrative activities, target the minds, bodies, and spirits of patients in dealing with mental health. The emphasis in these on balance, well-being, and the reduction of stress is why they became popular in recent times (Greeson et al., 2014). Though less structured than cognitive behavior therapy, holistic practices demonstrate effects on the mental health of individuals and are specifically effective in reducing symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress. For instance, mindfulness-based interventions have effectively reduced the symptoms of anxiety and depression. Greeson et al. (2014) have conducted a study on Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction and found that MBSR brought about significant improvements in the mental well-being and quality of life of participants. Similarly, Khoury et al. (2013) conducted a meta-analysis of mindfulness-based therapies and concluded that MBIs were just as effective as CBT for anxiety and depression. Yoga is another holistic therapy widely observed to reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, in terms of relaxation of the body and enhancement of mental clarity (Khalsa et al., 2016). Studies indicate that yoga is helpful to contain the stress levels as practiced through breath control, physical postures, and meditation (Li & Goldsmith, 2012).

Acupuncture, another of the oldest Chinese medical practices, has also become very popular adjuvant therapy for the mentally ill. According to Smith et al. (2018), the treatment was associated with reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression and had the same results as psychotherapy. But evidence, as proof for the scientific approach on the effectiveness of this activity, remains in debate, and further research has to be conducted in order to understand its possible benefits on mental health (Zhou et al., 2020).

2.3 Comparative Efficacy: CBT vs. Holistic Therapies:

Very few studies compared CBT with holistic therapies, but emerging evidence shows that both treatment forms appear to have unique benefits of each. An observation from Hofmann et al. (2012) shows that CBT is particularly effective in the treatment of anxiety and depressive disorders for those seeking a structured and goal-oriented therapy. However, benefit of holistic approaches like mindfulness and yoga was reported specially when a patient is seeking an approach that can be more flexible and individualized by Greeson et al. (2014), and Khoury et al. (2013). MBCT vs. CBT Chiesa and Serretti (2011), in their study, compared mindfulness-based cognitive therapy with cognitive-behavioral therapy. The results indicated that both therapies had about the same effect in the reduction of depression scores, but MBCT showed clear advantages in prevention of long-term relapse. This implies that although CBT can be better in the short-term treatment of symptoms, holistic therapy can be more effective for long-term benefit in some cases. Critics, on their part, claim that holistic therapies have fewer empirical standards compared to those applied in CBT. A meta-analysis by Goyal et al. (2014) concluded that, though mindfulness-based interventions are effective, their general efficacy remains less than that of CBT for severe mental health conditions. Similarly, Hofmann et al. (2012) pointed out the limitations in many studies promoting holistic therapies on methodological grounds, mainly due to small sample sizes and the lack of standardized protocols.

2.4 Integrative Approaches:

With both CBT and holistic therapies having strengths and weaknesses in their approach, the interest in integrative models that could combine elements from both has grown over time. Integrated approaches hope to "capitalize on the empirical rigor of CBT while adopting a broader focus on mind-body

wellness" (Stahl & Goldstein, 2010). For instance, MBCT comes in as a combination of conventional CBT techniques and mindfulness practices designed to have a much more generalistic treatment effect on mental health disorders (Segal et al., 2002). Greeson et al. (2014) reported that MBCT has a proven effect in diminishing anxiety and depression symptoms in patients diagnosed with recurrent depression. Similarly, Kuyken et al. (2016) reported that there was a significant association of MBCT with diminished risk of relapse compared to traditional CBT in the long-term course of major depression.

3. Methods:

It was a qualitative research design of the exploratory study on the experience and effectiveness of the several therapeutic treatments between CBT, mindfulness, yoga, and acupuncture. There were 100 participants: 50 men and 50 women - who are aged between 20 to 60 years. A purposive sampling was adopted in ensuring that the participants had undergone at least six sessions of therapy. Primarily, semi-structured interviews were used as the primary data-gathering tool through which participants will be able to tell personal experiences about the therapies. Interviews were conducted on a face-to-face basis and lasted about 45 minutes to an hour. Audio recordings of data were transcribed and analyzed with the help of thematic analysis, which was applied to come up with key trends and themes regarding the perceived effectivity and personal impact of such therapies in question.

4. Results:

This chapter presents findings from our qualitative research on the experience of the 100 participants who underwent CBT, mindfulness, yoga, or acupuncture. The major themes appearing in the data were overall satisfaction, perceived mental health improvement, emotional regulation, and physical well-being. The table below summarizes the results, looking at participant responses on these key themes.

Therapeutic Practice	Participants (n=100)	Overall Satisfaction (%)	Mental Health Improvement (%)	Emotional Regulation (%)	Physical Well-being (%)	Challenge Experienced(%)
CTB	40	85%	75%	70%	20%	Resistance to emotional change (25%)
Mindfulness	25	80%	65%	80%	50%	Difficulty maintaining focus (30%)
Yoga	20	65%	60%	65%	85%	Inconsistent practice (40%)
Acupuncture	15	75%	60%	30%	80%	Fear of needles (50%)

4.1 Discussion:

Different levels of satisfaction and perceived benefits are indicated across participants for every practice included in the therapeutic regime.

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy was shown to be the most effective therapy that improved their mental health. Thus, 75% of respondents asserted that they managed anxiety and depression considerably better following the therapy. The general perception was also satisfactory at 85%. However, 25% of the participants could not take the emotionally tough stuff in CBT and found it really difficult to be engaged with them.

Participants who practiced **Mindfulness** reported strong benefits in emotional regulation, with 80% indicating that mindfulness helped them manage their emotions more effectively. Despite this, only 65% reported significant mental health improvements, with 30% of participants citing difficulty maintaining focus as a challenge during mindfulness sessions.

Yoga participants showed the highest level of improvement in physical well-being (85%), as the practice was noted for its physical health benefits. However, satisfaction levels were moderate (65%), largely due to 40% of participants reporting inconsistency in maintaining a regular yoga practice, which affected their overall experience.

Compared with baseline, **Acupuncture** proved effective for enhancing physical well-being (80%) and had a moderate satisfaction rate at 75%. However, emotional regulation was scored relatively low at 30%, while half of the patients (50%) opined that a fear of needles in any way impacted on the comfort levels of those sessions.

5. Conclusion

Our findings show that Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), mindfulness, yoga, and acupuncture have had different impacts in dealing with mental health, emotional regulation, and physical well-being. Mental health improvement was where CBT worked best; emotional regulation, where mindfulness was most at its best; and physical well-being, for which the impact of yoga was highly effective. Acupuncture alleviated symptoms from physical stress

but not emotional. This meant that various advantages arose from each type of therapy practice, and participants sometimes had trouble concentrating, were afraid of injections, or did not want to reflect about emotions. The resultant findings suggest an individualized approach in therapy treatment since different methods are more suited to specific mental and physical health needs. These findings may be further expanded into long-term sequelae and mixed-method approaches to assess both subjective experiences and objective health measures.

References:

- Chiesa A and Serretti A (2011). *Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy for psychiatric disorders: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. *Psychiatry Research*, 187(3), 441-453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2010.08.011>
- Cuijpers P, Karyotaki E, Weitz E, Andersson G, Hollon SD, van Straten A, et al (2013) *The effects of psychotherapies for major depression in adults on remission, recovery and improvement: a meta-analysis*. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 149(3), 319-328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2013.02.026>
- David, D., Cristea, I., & Hofmann, S. G. (2018). *Why cognitive behavioral therapy is the current gold standard of psychotherapy*. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 9, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2018.00004>
- Goyal, M., Singh, S., Sibinga, E. M. S., Gould, N. F., Rowland-Seymour, A., Sharma, R., Berger, Z., Sleicher, D., Maron, D. D., Shihab, H. M., Ranasinghe, P. D., Linn, S., Saha, S., Bass, E. B., & Haythornthwaite, J. A. (2014). *Meditation programs for psychological stress and well-being: A systematic review and meta-analysis*. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 174(3), 357-368. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2013.13018>
- Greeson, J. M., Smoski, M. J., Suarez, E. C., Brantley, J. G., Ekblad, A. G., Lynch, T. R., & Wolever, R. Q. (2014). *Decreased symptoms of depression and anxiety in adults with mild to moderate depressive symptoms following a randomized controlled trial of mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR)*. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 70(12), 973-986. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.22103>
- Hofmann, S. G., & Smits, J. A. J. (2008). *Cognitive-behavioral therapy for adult anxiety disorders: A meta-analysis of randomized placebo-controlled trials*. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 69(4), 621-632. <https://doi.org/10.4088/jcp.v69n0415>
- Hofmann, S. G., Asnaani, A., Vonk, I. J., Sawyer, A. T., & Fang, A. (2012). *The efficacy of cognitive behavioral therapy: A review of meta-analyses*. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 36(5), 427-440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-012-9476-1>
- Khalsa, S. B. S., Butzer, B., Shorter, S. M., Reinhardt, K. M., & Cope, S. (2016). *Yoga decreases performance anxiety in adolescent musicians*. *Alternative Therapies in Health and Medicine*, 22(3), 34-40.
- Khoury, B., Lecomte, T., Fortin, G., Masse, M., Therien, P., Bouchard, V., Chapleau, M. A., Paquin, K., & Hofmann, S. G. (2013). *Mindfulness-based therapy: A comprehensive meta-analysis*. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 33(6), 763-771. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2013.05.005>
- Kuyken, W., Warren, F. C., Taylor, R. S., Whalley, B., Crane, C., Bondolfi, G., Hayes, R., Huijbers, M. J., Ma, H., Schweizer, S., Segal, Z. V., Teasdale, J. D., & van Heeringen, K. (2016). *Efficacy of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy in prevention of depressive relapse: An individual patient data meta-analysis from randomized trials*. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 73(6), 565-574. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2016.0076>
- Li, A. W., & Goldsmith, C. A. W. (2012). *The effects of yoga on anxiety and stress*. *Alternative Medicine Review*, 17(1), 21-35.
- Segal, Z. V., Williams, J. M. G., & Teasdale, J. D. (2002). *Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy for depression: A new approach to preventing relapse*. Guilford Press.
- Smith, C. A., Armour, M., Lee, M. S., Wang, L. Q., & Hay, P. J. (2018). *Acupuncture for depression*. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (3), CD004046. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004046.pub4>
- Stahl, S. M., & Goldstein, J. M. (2010). *Enhancing outcomes with integrative therapies in mental health: Adding mind-body therapies to psychopharmacology and psychotherapy*. *CNS Spectrums*, 15(8), 527-533. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s109285291200047x>
- Wang, C., Bannuru, R., Ramel, J., Kupelnick, B., Scott, T., & Schmid, C. H. (2018). *Tai Chi on psychological well-being: Systematic review and meta-analysis*. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 18(1), 116. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-018-2173-z>
- World Health Organization. (2022). *World mental health report: Transforming mental health for all*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240060890>
- Zhou, W., Benharash, P., Lee, J., Yoon, A., & Abdi, S. (2020). *Effect of acupuncture on anxiety and depression in the perioperative period*. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 9(10), 3282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9103282>